

A NOTE ON THE CONSTITUTION OF FORMIC ACID.

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The question of the constitution of formic acid has attracted considerable attention, chiefly because formic acid differs in some of its salient characteristics from the higher homologues in the fatty acid series. The highly reducing property of formic acid usually attributed to the presence in it of an aldehyde group is one which stands out prominent in this connection. Ray (*Nature*, 1934, 133, 646) concludes that the difference between formic acid and its higher homologues is due to the different structure of formic acid in which the hydrogen attached to the carbon is the ionisable atom and not the hydroxyl group as in the case of the higher fatty acids. He shows that the undissociated formic acid and its esters are not reducing agents and attributes the reduction to the formate ions as due to the presence of a "lone pair" of electrons in the carbon atom. Halasyam (*J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1935, 12, 813) quotes other evidence to support this view. This view, however, explains only the strikingly reducing property of the acid leaving unexplained some of the other exceptional properties of the acid, such as its highly acidic character and the absence of a formyl chloride or a formic anhydride

From Raman spectra studies, Venkateswaran (*Proc. Indian Acad. Sci.*, 1935, 2A, 615) has obtained conclusive evidence for the presence of a "CH" group in the formic acid molecule and of a "CHO" group in the formate ion. This is in agreement with the view put forward by Seshadri (Venkateswaran, *loc. cit.*) that the carboxyl group in the acid is linked to a hydrogen atom (aldehyde group), whereas in the homologues of formic acid the carboxyl is linked to the alkyl groups and that in the course of certain reactions, formic acid is capable of undergoing isomeric change to dihydroxymethylene.

The majority of evidence available from both the physical and chemical properties of the acid tends to confirm the view that there is in formic acid, a "CH" group. This note deals with a very striking piece of evidence in support of this latter view and is based on the well known biological reaction of formic acid studied in detail by Thunberg (*Skand. Arch. Physiol.*, 1920, 40, 1), and Quastel and Whetham (*Biochem. J.*, 1925, 19, 520)

and Quastel (*ibid.*, 1926, 20, 166). The last named has shown that the activation of formic acid is represented by the simple change,

in which (I) is the ordinary (or inactive) form of formic acid, while (II) represents the activated form. In view of the presence of two hydroxyl groups in the latter, formic acid should on activation act as a hydrogen donor. Quastel (*et al*) have indeed shown that this is actually the case. Curiously enough formic acid is the most powerful hydrogen donor in the fatty acid series and with the exception of some of the sugars is the most active hydrogen donor yet investigated. It has absolutely no reducing power *in vitro* on methylene blue, even in strongly alkaline solution. Quastel further substantiates the above points by taking substituted formic acid and shows that if for "OH" in (I), a radical acting in the same sense *e. g.*—NH₂ or—CH₃, is substituted, the resulting compounds should also act as hydrogen donors. Thus the activation of acetaldehyde is represented

where (IV) should have a powerful attraction for negative electricity. Owing to the non-polar nature of the CH₃-group, there should be an apparent diminution in the reducing power. It has thus been already shown that acetaldehyde is a hydrogen donor under suitable conditions (for example in the presence of *Bacillus coli*). The same is the case with formamide in which the amino group is polar.

Since formic acid has no action *in vitro* on methylene blue, it is clear that as a substrate it is in the inactive state when it does not act as hydro-

gen donator and the formula (I), must evidently represent the ordinary (or inactive) molecule.

It is known that formic acid is strictly monobasic and it may be asked how the dihydroxymethylene structure, which the substance exhibits on activation (with its two equivalent hydrogen atoms) can satisfy the avowedly monobasic character of the acid. It must, however, be remembered that the carbon of the COOH in formic acid is attached to the hydrogen by one of its negative bonds and to the OH-group by a positive bond, which tends to weaken the whole molecule and incidentally the bond between the hydrogen and oxygen in the OH, thus making possible a greater amount of dissociation, whereas the carbon atom in the higher acid is bound only by positive bonds with consequent greater stability and less dissociation. Thus the structure of formic and acetic acids may be written as follows.

There is, further, absolutely no evidence of the existence of an equilibrium mixture of the type, (I) $\rightleftharpoons$ (II), at any instance comparable to substances which exhibit tautomerism.

It is well known that formic acid cannot lose carbon dioxide, while carbonic acid can. It will be observed in the formula given below that the COOH group in formic acid is negative and in carbonic acid positive.

In the former three of the valences of carbon are positive and the fourth negative, while in carbonic acid all four valences are positive. The reducing action of formic acid is thus easily explicable from considerations of its electronic structure.

All these foregoing considerations show that for formic acid to act as a hydrogen donator, it has to get activated or in other words it has to bring about a change in its electronic structure. This occurs when the aldehyde structure of the ordinary acid assumes a dihydroxymethylene structure. Thus the already well known biological property of formic acid, which can be interpreted according to Quastel (*loc. cit.*) as due to a change in the electronic structure of the compound shows that, formic acid has in it a "CH" group when in the normal state changing to a dihydroxymethylene structure on activation. It is thus clear that the ionisable hydrogen is definitely the one attached to the hydroxyl group of formic acid just as in the case of the higher fatty acids and not the one attached to the carbon atom, and the old idea of attributing the exceptional properties of formic acid to the existence in it of an aldehyde group should be retained.

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